

Stellar Collisions and Exotic Populations in a Globular Cluster

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ABSTRACT

I present a study of the stellar populations and collision products in a simulated globular cluster with an age of 10 Gyr, modeled using MESA. The isochrone of the cluster was constructed to trace various evolutionary stages, including the main sequence (MS), sub-giant branch (SGB), red giant branch (RGB), horizontal branch (HB), and white dwarfs (WDs). Exotic objects such as blue stragglers (BSSs), blue lurkers (BLs), and yellow stragglers (YSSs) were added by considering single-single stellar collisions, with collision products evolved from the zero-age main sequence (ZAMS). The resulting BSSs, BLs, and YSSs showed properties consistent with observational studies.

Key words: Globular Clusters, Stellar Collisions, Blue Stragglers, Blue Lurkers, Yellow Stragglers, Hertzsprung-Russell diagram

1 INTRODUCTION

Globular clusters (GCs) are among the most ancient stellar systems, with ages shorter than that of the Universe. Over such long timescales, they undergo various physical processes driven by cluster dynamics. The dense central environment of a cluster provides ideal conditions for stellar collisions, leading to the formation of various exotic stellar populations.

One such exotic stellar population is that of Blue Straggler Stars (BSSs) discovered by A. Sandage (Sandage 1953). He identified stars that were brighter and bluer than the main sequence, lying above the main sequence turn-off (MSTO) in the color-magnitude diagram (CMD) of the globular cluster M3. These stars are termed Blue Straggler Stars (BSSs) because they appear to lag behind in evolution compared to normal stars. Since all stars in a cluster form at the same time, these stars should have evolved to later evolutionary stages such as the subgiant branch (SGB) or the red giant branch (RGB). Instead, BSSs appear rejuvenated, having gained mass through some abnormal process. The three primary formation pathways for BSSs are: (1) mass transfer via Roche lobe overflow (RLOF) in binary systems, leading to mass gain by the BSS progenitor (McCrea 1964); (2) stellar collisions in dense cluster environments (Hills & Day 1976); and (3) tightening and merger of inner binaries in a hierarchical triple system (Perets & Fabrycky 2009; Naoz & Fabrycky 2014). In this study, I focus exclusively on stellar collisions in dense cluster environments.

Individual stars in globular clusters may collide or merge in close binary systems, forming a more massive star (Hills & Day 1976; Leonard 1989). Collisions between two main-sequence (MS) stars are a key pathway for BSS formation. These physical collisions predominantly occur in the dense cores of star clusters, often while the stars remain on the MS. Due to the relatively low relative velocities

of stars in clusters compared to their surface escape speeds, MS-MS collisions generally result in mergers with minimal mass loss. The remnants of such collisions are complex and uncertain, but they typically exhibit high angular momentum, leading to rapid rotation and non-spherical shapes. Internal mixing within the merger product plays a crucial role, particularly in replenishing the core with unburned hydrogen, which significantly affects the lifetime of the merger product.

In addition to BSSs, Blue Lurkers (BLs) are another population formed via mass gain, but they do not appear brighter than the MSTO in the CMD. This could be due to either insufficient gained mass or small progenitors. As a result, the CMD jump for these stars is not large enough to place them above the MSTO. These stars are termed blue lurkers, defined as "BSS-type stars lying hidden in the MS below the MSTO" (Leiner et al. 2019). Past studies have identified blue lurkers in open clusters (Leiner et al. 2019; Subramaniam et al. 2020) and globular clusters (Dattatreya et al. 2023a).

Yellow Straggler Stars (YSSs) are believed to be evolved BSSs moving through the subgiant phase. In the CMD, YSSs appear brighter than the SGB and bluer than the RGB. Landsman et al. (1997) inferred that the yellow giant/YSS S1040 represents an evolved stage of a BSS formed via Case B mass transfer. Leiner et al. (2016) studied the YSS WOCs 1015 in the open cluster M67 using Kepler K2 observations and found its mass to be approximately twice that of the MSTO. Rain et al. (2021) identified 77 YSS candidates among 408 open clusters.

2 MESA SIMULATIONS

The Modules for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA) is an open-source stellar evolution code widely used for simulating the structure and evolution of stars across a broad range of masses, metallicities, and evolutionary stages (Paxton et al. 2015).

To evolve stars under the required globular cluster (GC) initial con-

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Table 1. Number of stars in various mass ranges as derived from the Kroupa IMF (Kroupa 2002)

Mass Range (M_{\odot})	Number of Stars
0.2 – 0.4	378,956
0.4 – 0.6	230,774
0.6 – 0.8	152,790
0.8 – 1.0	85,629
1.0 – 1.2	53,729
1.2 – 1.4	36,518
1.4 – 1.6	26,606
1.6 – 1.8	19,697
1.8 – 2.0	15,301

ditions, I started with the `low_z` inlist provided in the `test_suite` directory of MESA. I modified this inlist by including appropriate mass-loss prescriptions and setting a stopping condition of `max_age` at 10 Gyr. The cluster age was taken to be 10 Gyr, consistent with the observational ages of GCs (Krauss 1999). The metallicity was set to $Z = 0.001$, corresponding to $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.3$, which aligns with typical values observed in GCs (Harris 1996).

Using this inlist, I evolved stars of various masses starting from $0.2 M_{\odot}$ on the main sequence up to $\geq 0.882 M_{\odot}$, which evolve into white dwarfs by the end of 10 Gyr (Figure 1).

3 COLLISION PROBABILITIES

To find the collision probabilities at various timesteps across the 10 Gyr lifespan of the cluster, I considered the core number density to be 10^5 stars per cubic parsec, velocity dispersion to be 10 km/s, and the total number of stars in the core to be 10^6 .

I adopted the initial mass function (IMF) from Kroupa (2002), which is expressed as a broken power law $dN \propto m^{-\alpha} dm$, where $\alpha = 0.3$ for $m/M_{\odot} < 0.08$, $\alpha = 1.3$ for $0.08 \leq m/M_{\odot} < 0.5$, and $\alpha = 2.3$ for $m/M_{\odot} > 0.5$. I assumed all stars were formed in a single burst of star formation at $t = 0$ in our simulations. Table 1 gives the resulting number of stars from this IMF in various mass ranges.

The collision timescale (τ_{coll}) for an encounter can be estimated as $(n\sigma v_{\infty})^{-1}$, where n is the number density of stars, v_{∞} is the velocity dispersion, and σ is given by Equation 1 (Ivanova et al. 2006).

$$\sigma = \pi d_{\text{max}}^2 \left(1 + \frac{v_p^2}{v_{\infty}^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Here, $d_{\text{max}} = R_1 + R_2$, where R_1 and R_2 are the radii of the two colliding stars, and $v_p = \sqrt{\frac{2G(M_1+M_2)}{d_{\text{max}}}}$, where M_1 and M_2 are the masses of the two colliding stars. Table 2 provides the collision timescales for collisions between stars of various mass ranges.

The probability of collision at time (t) between a pair of stars with masses M_1 and M_2 can be sampled from a Poisson distribution as in Equation 2 (Ivanova et al. 2005).

$$P(t) = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{coll}}} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_{\text{coll}}}\right) \quad (2)$$

The probability of at least one collision occurring between N_1 stars of mass M_1 and N_2 stars of mass M_2 can be calculated as $1 - \exp(-N_1 N_2 P(t))$. Table 3 provides the collision probabilities for at least one collision for stars in different mass ranges and at various timestamps over the 10 Gyr lifespan.

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Table 2. Collision timescales (τ_{coll}) in Gyrs for collisions between stars of various mass ranges.

Mass Range (M_{\odot})	0.2 – 0.4	0.4 – 0.6	0.6 – 0.8	0.8 – 1.0
0.2 – 0.4	47.8	27.9	17.4	10.4
0.4 – 0.6	27.9	18.2	12.4	7.9
0.6 – 0.8	17.4	12.4	8.9	6.1
0.8 – 1.0	10.4	7.9	6.1	4.5

4 RESULTS

With the MESA simulations, I sampled an isochrone for the globular cluster stars at an age of 10 Gyr. Figure 1 shows the stars at various evolutionary stages, such as the main sequence (MS), subgiant branch (SGB), red giant branch (RGB), horizontal branch (HB), and white dwarfs (WDs).

I modified the isochrone by adding various exotic objects, such as blue stragglers (BSSs), blue lurkers (BLs), and yellow stragglers (YSSs). To achieve this, I calculated the collision probabilities as discussed in section 3. I considered mass ranges of 0.2-0.4, 0.4-0.6, 0.6-0.8, and 0.8-1.0 M_{\odot} . The motivation behind these mass ranges was to sample the complete main sequence of the globular cluster with a decent resolution, in order to identify a good number of candidate collision products of different types. The final collision product (or rejuvenated star) was evolved as if it restarted its evolution from the zero-age main sequence with an initial mass of $M_1 + M_2$ for the remaining time until the 10 Gyr age. Figure 2 shows the positions of the collision products in the HR diagram.

5 DISCUSSION

The MESA simulations provided a detailed isochrone for stars in the globular cluster with an age of 10 Gyr, offering insights into different evolutionary stages, including the MS, SGB, RGB, HB, and WDs, as shown in Figure 1. These stages serve as a baseline for understanding the typical single-star evolution in a globular cluster. I found the MSTO mass to be around $0.85 M_{\odot}$. This is close to the turnoff mass for NGC 362, which is approximately $0.8 M_{\odot}$ (Dattatreya et al. 2023a). NGC 362 has an $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.3$ and an age ≈ 11 Gyr, which is comparable to the initial conditions of our simulated globular cluster.

I also included exotic objects such as BSSs, BLs, and YSSs, which add complexity and a more realistic view of the stellar population. The addition of these exotic objects was motivated by the observed presence of such stars in globular clusters, often attributed to stellar collisions and mergers.

I classified BLs (Leiner et al. 2019; Subramaniam et al. 2020; Dattatreya et al. 2023a) as stars near the MSTO but unable to stand out from the MS in Figure 2. Stars with luminosities below the MSTO were classified as BLs. The ages for $0.9 M_{\odot}$ BLs were found to be 5-7 Gyr, while for $1.0 M_{\odot}$ BLs, the ages ranged from 1-3 Gyr. Dattatreya et al. (2023a) estimated the age and mass of their BLs to be approximately 5.5-10 Gyr and 0.82 - $0.92 M_{\odot}$, which aligns with our simulated BLs. They also estimated the T_{eff} and L/L_{\odot} for BLs using binary-fit SED analysis to be 6250-6750 K and 1.02-2.45, respectively. These values are comparable to our simulated BLs, with T_{eff} around 6500-7000 K and L/L_{\odot} ranging from 1.6-2.4.

I classified BSSs as stars that clearly stand out from the MSTO. The ages for $1.0 M_{\odot}$ BSSs were found to be 4-5 Gyr, while for 1.2

Figure 1. Isochrone of the globular cluster at 10 Gyr. Different evolutionary branches are labeled in red. Each grey marker represents a star's position in the HR diagram with its mass annotated. Extra data points added in the HB region to sample it properly.

Figure 2. Zoomed-in view of the isochrone after including the collisional products. The different types of collision products and normal stars are shown with their respective masses.

Table 3. Probability of at least one collision at different timestamps for masses in the ranges 0.2 – 0.4, 0.4 – 0.6, 0.6 – 0.8, and 0.8 – 1.0 M_{\odot} .

Timestamp (Gyr)		0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})
1	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.94
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.95	0.94	0.93	0.89
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.96	0.93	0.90	0.84
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.89	0.84	0.73
2	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.92
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.95	0.93	0.91	0.86
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.95	0.91	0.87	0.79
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.86	0.79	0.65
3	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.90
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.92	0.89	0.82
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.89	0.84	0.73
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.90	0.82	0.73	0.57
4	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.94	0.93	0.93	0.88
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.93	0.90	0.87	0.78
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.93	0.87	0.81	0.67
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.88	0.78	0.67	0.49
5	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.93	0.93	0.92	0.85
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.93	0.89	0.85	0.74
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.85	0.77	0.61
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.85	0.74	0.61	0.42
6	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.93	0.92	0.90	0.83
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.88	0.83	0.69
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.90	0.83	0.74	0.55
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.83	0.69	0.55	0.35
7	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.91	0.89	0.80
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.91	0.86	0.80	0.64
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.89	0.80	0.70	0.49
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.80	0.64	0.49	0.29
8	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.91	0.88	0.76
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.91	0.85	0.78	0.60
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.88	0.78	0.65	0.44
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.76	0.60	0.44	0.24
9	0.2 – 0.4 (M_{\odot})	0.92	0.90	0.86	0.73
	0.4 – 0.6 (M_{\odot})	0.90	0.83	0.75	0.55
	0.6 – 0.8 (M_{\odot})	0.86	0.75	0.61	0.39
	0.8 – 1.0 (M_{\odot})	0.73	0.55	0.39	0.20

M_{\odot} BSSs, the ages were 1-3 Gyr. The age for 1.4 M_{\odot} BSS is just 1 Gyr. For BSSs of mass higher than 1.4 M_{\odot} , the collision probabilities were too low, and I did not consider them as possible collision products. Comparing this with BSSs in NGC 362, [Dattatreya et al. \(2023b\)](#) reported masses in the range of 1-1.6 M_{\odot} , which aligns with our simulated BSS mass range. In general, BSS masses in globular clusters are found to be 1.2-1.5 M_{\odot} ([Fiorentino et al. 2014](#); [Raso et al. 2019](#)). [Dattatreya et al. \(2023b\)](#) also reported collisional BSS ages of 1.5-2.5 Gyr, consistent with our simulated BSSs. Furthermore, they found T_{eff} for collisional BSSs to be 7500-9500 K, matching our simulated BSS T_{eff} range of 7000-9500 K. The L/L_{\odot} for their BSSs ranged from 4-20, while our simulated BSSs had L/L_{\odot} values between 3-10.

Notably, [Figure 2](#) shows an interesting evolutionary trend for 1.0 M_{\odot} collision products. These stars are initially classified as BLs but evolve over time to become BSSs. This aligns with theoretical expectations, where BLs are considered "less-evolved" BSSs that do not stand out from the MSTO in the HR diagram.

I also identified one YSS candidate with a mass of 1.0 M_{\odot} and an age of 6 Gyr. YSSs are believed to be evolved BSSs, and the isochrone clearly illustrates this trend, with a 1.0 M_{\odot} star evolving

from a BL to a BSS and eventually becoming a YSS. I could not find any previous studies on YSSs in NGC 362 or other globular clusters. Studies on YSSs in open clusters exist, but they typically involve much more massive stars than those in globular clusters ([Leiner et al. 2016](#)).

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, I simulated the stellar populations of a globular cluster with an age of 10 Gyr using MESA, incorporating various evolutionary phases and exotic stellar objects like blue stragglers (BSSs), blue lurkers (BLs), and yellow stragglers (YSSs). The detailed isochrone provided insights into the mass, age, and luminosity distributions of these objects and their evolutionary connections. Our results are consistent with observational studies of similar globular clusters, such as NGC 362, demonstrating the reliability of our approach.

I assumed single-single star encounters as the sole mechanism for collisions, which provided a simplified view of the formation of exotic objects like BSSs and BLs. However, globular clusters are

environments where single-binary and binary-binary encounters are also significant contributors to the formation of collision products. Future studies should incorporate these interactions to present a more comprehensive picture of stellar dynamics and collision products in globular clusters.

Furthermore, our approach assumed that all collision products restart their evolution from the zero-age main sequence (ZAMS). While this simplification aids in modeling, it overlooks the complexities of real collision outcomes, such as the thermal and structural adjustments that occur during and after a collision. Future work should aim to include more realistic treatments of collision products, considering the detailed pre-collision history and post-collision structural evolution.

Another simplification in this study was the assumption of a constant core density over the 10 Gyr lifespan of the cluster. In reality, globular clusters are dynamical systems, undergoing processes like core collapse, mass segregation, and relaxation, which significantly affect core density over time. Incorporating time-dependent core density variations would provide a more realistic framework for studying stellar collisions and population evolution.

Overall, while this work offers valuable insights into the formation and evolution of exotic stellar objects in globular clusters, it highlights the need for future models to account for more complex dynamical interactions and physical processes to enhance our understanding of these fascinating systems.

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